

Prevalence of *Aspergillus* spp and *Penicillium* spp in Basterma and Sausage with special reference to ochratoxin

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Abstract

Many species of mould affected meat and meat products. Mycotoxins are highly toxic metabolites produced by certain types of moulds and are mainly associated with food poisoning outbreaks in human. In order to investigate the prevalence of *Aspergillus* spp and *Penicillium* spp in Basterma and sausage as well as the detection of Ochratoxin A, a total of 70 samples of Basterma and sausage (35 of each) were randomly collected from different markets in Port Said governorate, Egypt. The collected specimens were examined mycologically, where the mean mould count was $6.9 \times 10^2 \pm 1.2 \times 10^2$ and $2.4 \times 10^2 \pm 2.7 \times 10^2$ in sausage and Basterma respectively. The prevalence of *Aspergillus* spp in sausage and Basterma was (85.7%) and (45.7%), respectively. *A. flavus* was the most predominant *Aspergillus* spp isolated from Basterma and sausage with prevalence (28.57%) and (25.71%) respectively, while the prevalence of *A. niger* in sausage and Basterma was (31.42%) and (14.28%), respectively. *A. ochraceus* could be isolated from sausage with prevalence (14.28%). The prevalence of *Penicillium* spp. was (42.83%) and (8.57%) in Basterma and sausage respectively, *P. corylophilum*, *P. citrinum*, *P. griseofulvum* were the most predominant species isolated from Basterma, their frequencies were (11.42%), (8.57%), (8.57%), respectively. *P. purpurenum* is the only isolated *Penicillium* spp from sausage with prevalence (8.57%). Qualitative and quantitative estimation of ochratoxin A was carried out on the collected samples and strains, where all the tested samples were negative for ochratoxin A, while 3 isolates of *A. ochraceus* originated from sausage were positive with a mean value of 12 ± 4.16 mg/L. In conclusion, Basterma and sausage were highly contaminated with *Aspergillus* spp and *Penicillium* spp which may gain access during the manufacturing process or with food additives leading to high economic losses and have a public health hazard due to the production of ochratoxin.

Keywords: Basterma, *Aspergillus*, Mycotoxin, Sausage, food poisoning

Introduction

Many strains of moulds are widely distributed in nature and may affect our food supply because of its contamination due to lack of sanitation and handling procedures. Contaminated feed is the main source for mycotoxin infection of farm animal (Sayed *et al.*, 2000, Elfeil *et al* 2012 and Sedeik *et al.* 2018). The lack of

attention to the hygienic design of factory plant and cleaning and sanitation procedures can lead to yeast and mould contamination of products. This is particularly problematic in plants producing low water activity and low pH products. Factories producing fermented products can be at real risk from yeast and mould contamination (Betts, 2014 and

Algammal and Elfeil 2015) which considered a high risk due to the ability of their toxic strains in production of highly toxic chemical substances referred as mycotoxins, which constitute potential and a real risk to public health due to the possibility of causing tumors or inducing organ damage due to repeated ingestion of subacute levels of mycotoxins (**Varman and Evans 1991, Eid et al 2016 and Badawi et al 2016**). Contamination of some meat additives with different mould and mycotoxins like ochratoxin was the major source of contamination of the manufactured meat products. (**Waleed et al., 2013 Abouelmaatti et al 2013, Elfeil et al 2016**) ochratoxin A is a toxic fungal secondary metabolite. Several studies have shown that OTA has nephrotoxic, immunotoxic, teratogenic, carcinogenic and possibly neurotoxic and genotoxic properties (**Miraglia and Brera 2002, Elhady et al. 2018 and Enany et al. 2018**). This work was planned to investigate the prevalence of *Aspergillus* spp and *penicillium* spp in Basterma and sausage as well as detection of ochratoxin A.

Material and methods

Sampling

A total of 70 random samples of Basterma and sausage (35 of each) were collected from different markets in Port Said governorate, Egypt. The collected samples were kept in sterile polyethylene bags and preserved in an ice box then transferred to the laboratory under complete aseptic condition without undue delay to be examined mycologically.

Sample preparation

The collected samples were prepared according to the methods described by

(**APHA, 2001**). Twenty-five grams from each sample were carefully and aseptically homogenized in a blender with 225 ml of sterile peptone water 0.1% to form a dilution of 1:10, from which tenth fold serial dilutions were accomplished up to 10^6 .

Determination of total mould count (ISO, 2008)

One ml of the previously prepared serial dilution was separately poured into duplicated Petri dishes carefully and mixed with Dichloran Rose Bengal Chloramphenicol (DRBC) agar, incubated at 25°C for 5-7 days. The incubated plates were examined for mould growth and then transferred onto Sabouraud's dextrose slope agar to be incubated at room temperature for 5 days and kept for further identification. The mould counted /gm was separately calculated and recorded.

Identification of *Aspergillus* spp and *penicillium* spp (Pitt and Hocking, 2009)

a. Microscopical examination

The macroscopical examination of mould colonies included the rate and pattern of growth, as color, texture, basal and surface mycelia, reverse of colony and the rate of colony growth and diameter. The examination was carried out by using a magnifying hand lens.

b. Microscopical examination

From the periphery of 5-7 days old colony, a triangular piece was transferred to a clean glass slide, with 2 mycological needles, the piece of the colony was distributed with one to two drops of lactophenol stain and then covered by a clean cover slip, followed by gentle pressure to remove the excess of fluid and air bubbles as well as to depress the hyphae and other structures for facilitating microscopic examination. The prepared

slides were examined under low power and oil immersion lenses to characterize the morphological structures of the mould growth concerning the conidial stage, head, vesicle, stigmata, conidiophore, and conidia. Also, the Hulle cells or other hyphal peculiarities, Sclerotia and ascospore stage were observed and recorded.

Extraction of ochratoxin A residues in Basterma and sausage

Mycotoxins were extracted from the collected Basterma and sausage specimens according to the methods described by (Stubblefield *et al.*, 1982). Thin layer chromatography was carried out for detection of mycotoxins as described by (Howell and Taylor, 1981). Plates were visualized under short and long UV light.

Screening of the isolated *A. ochraceous* strains for production of Ochratoxin A. Cultivation of *A. ochraceous* strains and extraction of ochratoxin A. (Davis *et al.*, 1966)

The isolated strains of *A. ochraceous* were inoculated onto 50 ml of yeast extract solution containing 15 %sucrose. The inoculated flasks were incubated at 25⁰C for 21 days. At the end of incubation period, 25 ml of chloroform were added, and the mixture was thoroughly mixed for one minute in ultraturax apparatus. The mixture was then centrifuged (3000 rpm) for 10 minutes where the chloroform layer was decanted, the chloroform extraction was repeated only once. One ml ethanol, 3gm copper-(111)-hydroxide, carbonate and from 5-10gm anhydrous sodium sulphate were added to the chloroform extract, mixed well and filtrated. The filtrate was then evaporated by warming on boiling water bath till dryness. The

residue was cooled and resuspended in exactly 5 ml of chloroform.

Qualitative and Quantitative Estimation of ochratoxin A:

Chromatographic plates were examined for qualitative estimation of ochratoxin A. Colors and intensities of the unknown spots were compared with those of the standard reference ochratoxin A (Sigma, USA). Samples and isolates extract which were found to contain mycotoxins by the qualitative technique were further estimated quantitatively according to (Schullerand and van, 1981). The mycotoxins concentration in the sample extracts determined by matching the fluorescence intensities of the toxin spots in the sample with those of the standard.

Results

Total mould count

In the present work, the mean mould count was $6.9 \times 10^2 \pm 1.2 \times 10^2$ and $2.4 \times 10^2 \pm 2.7 \times 10$ in sausage and Basterma, respectively as illustrated in Table (1).

Prevalence of *Aspergillus* spp in examined Basterma and sausage

As described in Table (2), the prevalence of *Aspergillus* spp in sausage and Basterma was (85.69%) and (45.71%), respectively. *A. flavus* was the most predominant *Aspergillus* spp isolated from Basterma and sausage with prevalence (28.57%) and (25.71%) respectively, while the prevalence of *A. niger* in sausage and Basterma was (31.42%) and (14.28%), respectively. *A. ochraceus*, *A. terreus* and *A. niveus* could be isolated from sausage with prevalence (14.28%), (8.57%) and (5.71%), respectively, while from sausage samples and *A. sydowii* could be detected in Basterma with prevalence (2.86%).

Prevalence of *penicillium* spp in examined Basterma and sausage

As described in Table (3), the prevalence of *Penicillium* spp. In Basterma and sausage was (42.83%) and (8.57%) respectively, *P. corylophilum*, *P. citrinum*, *P. griseofulvum* were the most predominant species isolated from Basterma samples, their frequencies were (11.43%), (8.57%), (8.57%), respectively. *P. oxalicum*, *P. variable* and *P. crustosum* were isolated from Basterma with prevalence (5.71%), (5.71%) and (2.86%), respectively, while

P. purpurgenum only detected in sausage samples with prevalence (8.57%).

Estimation of ochratoxin A

In the present study, Ochratoxin A couldn't be detected in the examined Basterma and sausage samples, while 3 isolates of *A. ochraceus* originated from sausage were positive for ochratoxin A. The minimum detection level was 4.8 mg/L while the maximum detection level was 19.2 mg/L and the mean value was 12 ± 4.16 mg/L.

Table (1): Total mould counts (cfu/g) in the examined Basterma and sausage

Meat products	Total mould count (cfu/g)		
	Minimum	Maximum	Mean(\pm SE)
Basterma	1×10	6×10^2	$2.4 \times 10^2 \pm 2.7 \times 10$
Sausage	9×10	3.4×10^4	$6.9 \times 10^2 \pm 1.2 \times 10^2$

Table (2): Prevalence of *Aspergillus* spp in the examined Basterma and sausage

<i>Aspergillus</i> species	Basterma n=35		Sausage n=35	
	No of +ve samples	Percentage	No of +ve samples	Percentage
<i>A. flavus</i>	10	28.57	9	25.71
<i>A. niger</i>	5	14.28	11	31.42
<i>A. niveus</i>	-	-	2	5.71
<i>A. ochraceus</i>	-	-	5	14.28
<i>A. sydowii</i>	1	2.86	-	-
<i>A. terreus</i>	-	-	3	8.57
Total	16	45.71	30	85.69

Table (3): Prevalence of *penicillium* spp in the examined Basterma and sausage

Isolated <i>Penicillium</i> Species	Basterma		Sausage	
	No	%	No	%
<i>P. citrinum</i>	3	8.57	-	-
<i>P. corylophilum</i>	4	11.42	-	-
<i>P. crustosum</i>	1	2.85	-	-
<i>P. griseofulvum</i>	3	8.57	-	-
<i>P. oxalicum</i>	2	5.71	-	-
<i>P. purpurgenum</i>	-	-	3	8.57
<i>P. variable</i>	2	5.71	-	-
Total	15	42.83	3	8.57

Discussion

Moulds are ubiquitous microorganisms and widely distributed in nature, so could easily gain access to meat and meat products through contaminated tools or air dust resulting in food poisoning outbreaks

(Stagnitta *et al.*, 2006). In the present study, the mean mould count was $6.9 \times 10^2 \pm 1.2 \times 10^2$ and $2.4 \times 10^2 \pm 2.7 \times 10$ in sausage and Basterma, respectively in Table (1). The results of the examined Basterma samples were nearly similar to

those obtained by (Hussein, 2008) and (Ouf *et al.*, 2010) who reported that mean counts (cfu/g) $2.8 \times 10^2 \pm 37.4$. While lower values were recorded by (Mousa *et al.*, 2014) and (Ebraheem and Mohamed 2012) who, found that mean total mould count of Basterma samples (cfu/g) was $1.22 \times 10^2 \pm 0.49 \times 10^2$. The higher incidence occurred in the examined Basterma may be due to they are raw not heat treated beside the addition of some meat additives. The results of the mean of total mould count of sausage in this work are nearly similar to (Fatema, 2016) who reported that the mean value was $8.7 \times 10^2 \pm 4.4 \times 10^2$ (cfu/g). lower mean value was obtained by (Morshdy *et al.*, 2015) which was $11 \times 10^2 \pm 3 \times 10^2$, also low values were reported by (El-Tabiy, 2006) and (Hussein, 2008). In the present work, the prevalence of *Aspergillus spp* in Basterma and sausage was (85.7%) and (45.71%), respectively Table (2). *A. flavus* was the most predominant *Aspergillus spp* isolated from Basterma and sausage with prevalence (28.57%) and (25.71%) respectively, while the prevalence of *A. niger* in in sausage and Basterma was (31.42%) and (14.28%) respectively. Furthermore, other *Aspergillus spp* were isolated from the examined sausage samples including; *A. ochraceus* (14.28%), *A. terreus* (8.57 %) and *A. niveus* (5.71%). The obtained results are nearly similar to those reported by (Ismail *et al.*, 2013; Eleiwa and El-Diasty, 2014; Morshdy *et al.*, 2015 and Abo El yazeed *et al.*, 2015) who reported that *Aspergillus* species were the most predominant mould species isolated from meat products samples.

In the present work, the most prevalent species were *A. flavus* followed by *A.*

niger which agreed with (Ebraheem and Mohamed, 2012) who found that the predominant species of *Aspergillus* in Basterma were *A. flavus* and *A. niger* and nearly similar to (Mousa *et al.*, 2014) who demonstrated *A. flavus* in Basterma (26 %). The obtained results in sausage are nearly similar to (Abo Al- yazeed *et al.*, 2015) who isolated *A. niger* with prevalence (30%), followed by *A. flavus* (20%). In the present work, *A. ochraceus* found only in sausage with prevalence (14.28%) which is nearly agreed with (Mousa *et al.*, 2014), while was higher than those obtained by (Abo Al- yazeed *et al.*, 2015) who isolated *A. ochraceus* in prevalence (10%) and lower than those obtained by (Iacumin *et al.*, 2011) who reported that sausages samples were highly contaminated with *A. ochraceus* (34%). In the present study as described in Table (3), the prevalence of *Penicillium spp*. In Basterma and sausage was (42.83%) and (8.57%) respectively, *P. corylophilum*, *P. citrinum*, *P. griseofulvum* were the most predominant species isolated from Basterma samples, their frequencies were (11.43%), (8.57%), (8.57%), respectively. *P. oxalicum*, *P. variable* and *P. crustosum* were isolated from Basterma with prevalence (5.71%), (5.71%) and (2.86%), respectively, while *P. purpurgenum* only detected in sausage samples with prevalence (8.57%). These results are similar to those obtained by (Khalifa, 2015) who isolated *P. citrinum* in 12% of the examined Basterma samples. On the other hand, *P. griseofulvum* was isolated from 12 % of the examined sausage samples. In the present study, Ochratoxin A couldn't be detected in the examined Basterma and

sausage samples, while 3 isolates of *A. ochraceus* originated from sausage were positive for ochratoxin. The minimum detection level was 4.8 mg/L while the maximum detection level was 19.2 mg/L and the mean value was 12 ± 4.16 mg/L. *A. ochraceus* is the best-known species of ochratoxin producing *Aspergillus*. It grows at moderate temperatures and at a high-water activity.

In conclusion, Basterma and sausage were highly contaminated with *Aspergillus* spp and *Penicillium* spp which may gain access during the manufacturing process or food additives leading to high economic losses and have a public health hazard due to the production of ochratoxin. So, Meat processing plants should be hygienically constructed and supplied with good equipment and utensils which easily cleaned and disinfected and Proper sanitary precautions of the utensils, equipment and tools must be applied.

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